

Voltametric Studies of Fe(III), Co(II) and Ni(II) in Molten Acetanilide

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D. C. and A. C. polarised voltametric studies in molten acetanilide at 135° have been reported. Platinum, graphite and stainless steel electrodes have been employed *in situ* under different concentrations of supporting electrolytes. The observed potential differences between the couples, platinum-graphite and stainless steel-graphite in presence of 0.1 M KSCN in molten acetanilide are 0.11 and 0.425 v respectively, whereas the corresponding values in 0.1 M LiClO₄ are the same, 0.03 v. The Q-values from the oscillograms of iron, cobalt and nickel in the molten acetanilide at the stationary solid electrodes have been measured and interpreted in conjunction with D. C. polarograms on the basis of reactions/adsorption occurring at the surface of electrodes.

SOLID electrode D. C. and A. C. polarization techniques have played an increasing part in the recent interest of the chemical industry in organic oxidation-reduction and catalytic interfacial phenomenon^{1,2}. Frumkin³ interpreted the surface phenomenon based upon adsorption and capacitance. Several excellent accounts of electrochemistry of molten salts have been published⁴⁻⁵ but literature regarding organic melts⁶ is rather scarce. Earlier, Anand⁷ reported the study of alkali metals in molten acetamide. The present paper describes an attempt to obtain conditions for D. C. polarograms and oscillograms in fused acetanilide melt at 135° with different stationary electrodes with an object to develop working current-potential curves.

Experimental

All chemicals were of analytical or reagent grade. D. C. polarograms were recorded as reported⁷ earlier. An electrical circuit used for polarizing the electrode with a controlled A. C. was fabricated after to Heyrovsky and Kalvoda⁸ with some modification as reported earlier⁹. Systronic D. C. oscilloscope 505 D (dual trace) was employed for observation and recording of oscillograms. The oscillograms were photographed with the help of an oscilloscope camera. Some representative photographs of the oscillograms of Fe, Co and Ni in molten acetanilide in presence of LiClO₄ at different electrodes have been shown in Fig. 1.

Electrodes and Pretreatment : Platinum electrodes were constructed by sealing B & S 24 and 26-gauge wires into glass tubes¹⁰. Commercial graphite rods generally used in D. C. motors and dry cells, after grinding with a fine emery paper grade 600 and SIA 6, were employed. Wax impregnated rods were also used but before immersion in the melt they were kept in the hot oven maintained at 135±1°. For steel electrodes, different strips

Fig. 1

were cut from non-magnetic Devi Dayal stainless steel sheet and polished with cotton buff as pretreatment.

Results and Discussion

Effect of electrodes : In D. C. polarography the current-voltage curves using LiClO_4 as supporting electrolyte in acetanilide melt at 135° have been obtained. Increasing cathodic polarization was employed to obtain all the current-voltage curves. Platinum-graphite, graphite-platinum, steel-graphite and graphite-steel electrode assemblies in acetanilide melt with and without the supporting electrolyte were used to record current-voltage curves. The half-wave potentials and the experimental slopes calculated according to the methods of Black and de Vries¹¹ and Laitinen *et al.*¹² are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—HALF-WAVE POTENTIALS AND VALUES OF SLOPE OBTAINED FOR Fe, Co AND Ni WITH RESPECT TO Pt. SOLVENT : MOLTEN ACETANILIDE AT 135°

Compound	Supporting electrolyte	$-E_{1/2}$ v	Slope observed mV	Slope theoretical*	Value of n
Solvent (At graphite)	LiClO_4	1.10	175	186	1 (for Li^+)
Solvent (At Platinum)	LiClO_4	1.475	164	186	1
FeCl_2 (Pt)	„	1.325	147	186	1
				93	2
				62	3
CoCl_2	„	1.09	192	186	1
				93	2
NiCl_2	„	0.73	130	186	1
				93	2
Solvent (At graphite)	KSCN	—	—	186	1
Solvent (At Platinum)	KSCN	0.605	167	186	1 (for K^+)
FeCl_2 (Pt)	„	0.95	278	186	1
				93	2
				62	3
CoCl_2	„	—	—	—	—
NiCl_2	„	1.07	210	186	1
				93	2

* Due to Delimarskii *et al.*

Many studies of electrode processes in melts are not sufficiently refined to require a precise knowledge of potential differences. Any large and unreactive conductor such as Pt^{13} , Ag^{14} , Graphite¹⁵ etc. immersed in the melt will function as non-polarizable and hence *in situ* may be readily employed as reference. The behaviour of graphite electrode as anode as well as reference appears more pronounced in presence of supporting electrolyte in conjunction with platinum electrode in acetanilide melt than in conjunction with steel. The difference of values of slopes between the experimental and theoretical values indicates that the process is not diffusion controlled. Delimarskii *et al.*¹⁶ believe that in a number of cases the slope of relation

$$\frac{\Delta E}{\Delta \log \left[\frac{i}{i_a - i} \right]} = \frac{2.3 RT}{nF}$$

is very close to the theoretical. An interesting observation in case of KSCN as supporting electrolyte is that the reduction waves of iron(III) and nickel(II) appear more negative to potassium with reference to graphite as anode. Cobalt(II) gives no reduction wave in presence of KSCN but in LiClO_4 a very well defined wave appears.

There appears no marked effect of concentration between 0.05 to 0.25M of KSCN or LiClO_4 on the observed values of potential differences of the platinum-graphite and stainless steel-graphite couples. The observed potential differences between the couples platinum-graphite and stainless steel-graphite in presence of 0.1M KSCN in molten acetanilide are 0.11 and 0.425 v respectively, whereas the corresponding values in 0.1M LiClO_4 are the same, 0.03 v.

Q-values : According to Heyrovsky⁸ the quotient Q is more useful than the value of potential which gives the relative position of indentation on the derivative curve $dE/dt=f(E)$. The upper part of the derivative curve represents a cathodic process and the lower one, an anodic process. The Q-values Table 2, vary between 0 and 1 and are independent of the reference electrode as reported by Heyrovsky.

TABLE 2—Q-VALUES OF Fe, Co AND Ni IN MOLTEN ACETANILIDE AT 135°

System	Cathode	Cathodic			Anodic			Photo No.
		1	2	3	1	2	3	
Acetanilide	+							
LiClO_4	Pt	0.33	0.55	0.78	0.33	0.55	0.78	1
LiClO_4	Gr	0.21	0.41	0.74	0.24	0.44	0.74	2
FeCl_2	Gr	0.24	0.48	0.76	0.28	0.50	0.80	3
„	Pt	0.25	0.50	0.79	0.25	0.50	0.75	4
CoCl_2	Gr	0.20	0.40	0.67	0.20	0.43	0.70	5
„	Pt	0.16	0.44	0.76	0.22	0.53	0.84	6
NiCl_2	Gr	0.20	0.48	0.86	0.17	0.48	0.80	7
„	Pt	0.16	0.44	0.76	0.22	0.53	0.84	8

Gr=graphite.

The differences in the Q-values of the cathodic and anodic parts of the derivative curve $dE/dt=f(E)$, may be attributed to some irreversibility and also to the faster rate of redox process than the frequency of A. C. polarization. In case of steel electrode such a phenomenon is absent and practically only an ellipse appears. Laitinen and Liu¹⁸ postulated adsorption on platinum for Co and Ni in fused salts in order to account for phase angles in their studies on faradaic impedance. A similar observation is evident from oscillogram (Fig. 1.6) when CoCl_2 in molten acetanilide containing LiClO_4 as supporting electrolyte is subjected to A. C. polarised study at platinum as cathode.

Further, rotating platinum electrode method gives no specific wave in the forward direction of cathodic polarization in Fe^{3+} , Co^{2+} and Ni^{2+} in the fused acetanilide. However, in the backward direction a wave has been observed in the case of Ni^{2+} , when the speed of rotation was about 600 RPM. But when the speed of rotation was reduced to about 300 RPM, two steps conforming to one- and two-electron reduction were noticed.

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